

Does Audit Fees and Auditor's Independence Influence Audit Quality? Evidence from a Weak Corporate Setting

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Abstract

In this paper, we examine whether audit fees and independence affect audit quality in the context of Nigeria poor corporate governance setting. We use a sample of 12 quoted industrial goods firms from the Nigerian Exchange Group over 2006-2020, yielding 180 observations. We provide the first evidence on the effect of audit fees on audit quality. We also provide evidence on the influence of audit independence on audit quality. We established that audit fees lead to improved audit quality. We similarly established that audit independence would lead to improve audit quality. Consistent with the signaling theory, we conclude that audit fees and audit independence are determinants of and more likely to lead to better audit quality. These findings offer a promising future to stakeholders to understand better a robust and strong link between audit fees and independence on one hand and audit quality on the other. However, the findings are limited to firms within the sector as the choice sector is open to debate since others are researchable. Also, the findings may have been affected by the methods and model selected; using broader set of variables that can act as proxies could be considered.

Keywords: *Audit Fees, Audit Independence, Audit Quality, Listed Firms, Nigeria*

1. Introduction

Audit quality (AQ) is questionable among corporations in Nigeria and the World at large. The facts of the case of Cadbury is still fresh in our memory. Also, several banks followed suite; Afribank, Diamond Bank, Intercontinental Bank, Reliance Bank, and host of others. There is a low quality in the process leading to the final preparation of audit report in Nigeria. There is also the issue of hiring poor quality audit firms in order to circumvent the high cost of engaging any of the Big4 audit firms. In addition, audit failures which involved international corporations such as Enron, WorldCom, Global Crossing, ImClone, and Tyco, etc., have increased doubt about audit quality of reports. This is the situation that calls for the engagement of good audit firms in order to guaranty quality audit report. AQ is a formal expression of opinion, or qualification issued by audit firm as a result of external audit, as part of quality assurance recommended by corporate governance codes. It is simply a joint responsibility of top management and the board of directors. Usually, the top management in active collaboration with the audit committee of the board ensures that a good audit firm is hired.

AQ is determined by a number of both internal and external factors, including audit firm's professional knowledge, skills, skepticism, standards compliance, working conditions, audit duration, quality control, firm's integrity, technical competence, quality of audit partners, firm's reputation and partners' technical competence. However, the focus of this article is restricted to audit fees and audit independence and how they bring their bearing on AQ. There are three parts of AQ that must be mentioned: plan, process and report. Audit cannot be said to be of quality unless and until the process is well planned and articulated and the report is consistent with applicable standards and guidelines.

Audit fees (AF) refer to all reasonable costs incurred by corporations in order to pay audit firms. So, it is anticipated that high audit fees would attract high quality audit firms and by consequences, there would be improvement in AQ. It is essential to note that this fee varies widely depending on the engagement locus of the audit firm and the variety of services provided. Fees paid in respect of mandatory audit may not be a subject to be determined by contingencies or and provision of other services. However, fees paid in connection with non-statutory audits may be a subject of several volatile factors.

Similarly, audit independence (AI) is crucial in ensuring AQ; because humans are involved. It refers to a system of checks and balances that ensure that the external auditor has no financial interest in the corporations being audited. The audit firm must be independent even in mental attitude towards the assignment. The auditor must be without bias with respect to the client since would lacking that impartiality is necessary for the dependability of audit findings. This is not to say that the auditor should be a prosecutor but an impartial judge on matters relating to audit engagement. There are major threats to the independence of the external auditor or audit firm. These threats include but not limited to the integrity and reliability of auditor report, self-interest, self-review, advocacy, familiarity, and intimidation. Despite these threats, audit independence is anticipated to lean towards improving AQ.

Several stakeholders stand to benefit from this paper: audit committee (AC) members, top management, board of directors, shareholders, regulators, researchers, to mention a few of them. The AC is shouldered with responsibility of recommending auditor to be appointed by the board of directors in order to ensure that quality audit is carried out. The findings of this paper would be useful to them in providing the environment in which the external auditor is appointed. Top management would come to appreciate and understand the statutory standards regarding audit engagement and how both audit fees and independence contribute to ensuring AQ improvement. The members of the board of directors are shouldered with the overall responsibility of ensuring that the audit report is of quality and that investors, creditors, users, etc. are not misinformed. Other stakeholders have varying needs of audit report and it is board's onerous responsibility to ensure that it is delivered. The paper is divided into five sections: introduction, literature review, methods, results and conclusions.

2. Literature Review

The agency theory submits that audit fees and auditor's independence affect AQ. The econometric model predicts that the relationships are both positively significant and suggests that corporations that pay high audit fees and ensure that the auditors are independent are connected with higher AQ because the board of directors are in a position to get the external auditors to carry out a good audit. The theory assumes that members of the board of directors are under contractual obligations with shareholders to ensure that the audit firm engaged, deliver a quality audit report which would be used by stakeholders for varying investment or credit decisions.

2.1 Audit Fees and AQ

Previous studies have found evidence linking audit fees and audit independence with AQ. Although, mixed results have been reported, the majority of the studies reported positive and significant findings. For example, Hoitash et al. (2007) examined fees paid to auditors and AQ during 2000-2003. They documented a statistically significant negative association. Similarly, Choi et al. (2010) examined AQ and audit fees and found that audit fees are negatively associated with AQ. Yuniarti (2011) examined audit fees and AQ in Bandung, West Java, Indonesia and found that audit fees and quality of audit are significant. Asthana and Boone (2012) found that AQ declines as audit fees increase in magnitude.

Further, Rahmina and Agoes (2014) assessed audit fee and AQ and finding showed that audit fee and AQ are positively influenced. Eshleman and Guo (2014) reexamined audit fees and AQ and found a negative link. Idawati (2014) analyzed the influence of audit fee on AQ of 103 Public Accountant Firms in Indonesia and found that audit fee influenced AQ. Also, Suseno (2013) reconnoitered audit fees and AQ of 73 public accountant offices in Indonesia. Findings depicted that audit fees significantly influenced the auditing quality. Hosseiniakani et al. (2014) reviewed and summarized the effect of audit fees on AQ and found that audit fees were found to be able to affect AQ significantly. Krauß et al. (2015) investigated audit fee and AQ in German using 2,334 observations over 2005-2010; the results demonstrated that positive audit fees are negatively associated with AQ. Also, Corbella et al. (2015) used

1583 firm-year observations data from Italy over 1998–2011 to examine audit fees and AQ. Their results indicated that the total amount of fees paid to the auditor was lower for companies audited by a Big 4, measure of AQ in this study. Meanwhile, Jung et al. (2016) during 2008 to 2013, interrogated data on audit fees and AQ over adoption of IFRS in Korea and found no significant relationship pre-IFRS adoption. Conversely, the connection turns positive during post-IFRS adoption. Zamzami et al. (2017) examined the effects of audit fee on AQ in Indonesia. The study observed that audit fee has no significant effects on the AQ.

Kuntari et al. (2017) assessed the effect of audit fees on AQ of 14 firms in Semarang in 2016. The findings showed that audit fees and AQ has a significant positive effect. Also, Pham et al. (2017) assessed the effects of audit fees on AQ of 192 corporations for 2006-2014. Findings suggested that the more audit fees the auditors receive, the lower AQ they provide. Gunn et al. (2019) contributed to the audit fees-AQ debate by arguing that the AQ (Big 4) leads to higher audit fees. Salehi et al. (2017) investigated the amount of downward pressure on audit fees and its effect on AQ of 104 listed companies in Iran and found a positive significant relationship. Ilechukwu (2017) scrutinized audit fee and AQ in Nigeria over 2011 and 2016 and showed that audit fee and AQ have positive but insignificant effect. Further, Ibrahim and Ali (2018) assessed the impact of audit fees on AQ of listed conglomerates in Nigeria over 2004 to 2015. The paper observed that audit fees have positive impact on company AQ.

Also, Wiguna et al. (2019) analyzed the influence of audit fees on AQ of 70 Public Accounting Firms in Bali, Indonesia that were registered in the IAPI 2019 directory. They argued that audit fee and AQ are positively significant. Meidawati and Assidiqi (2019) evaluated audit fees independence and AQ of 45 Accounting Firms in Semarang City, Indonesia. Findings indicated that audit fee and AQ are negatively related, and that auditor's independence and AQ have no effect. Hai et al. (2019) assessed 267 auditors to measure audit fees and quality of audit work and found that audit fee impact on quality of audit. Sari et al. (2019) analyzed the effect of audit fee on AQ of 50 manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange over 2015-2017. The results of this study indicated that audit fee do not affect AQ. Also, Wahyuni et al. (2019) examined the influence of audit fees on AQ of 87 Public Accounting Firms in Bali, Indonesia. The test results showed that audit fees have a significant effect on AQ. Yanti and Wijaya (2020) assessed audit fees and AQ for 2015-2018 and found no effect.

Further, Gandia and Huguet (2020) examined audit fees and AQ in Spain and found inverse association. Behrend et al. (2020) used a sample of public firms in the Korean audit market to assess audit fees and AQ. They did not find a significant association between high audit fees and AQ. Also, Cho et al. (2021) examined audit fees and AQ and did not find a significant relation. Chang et al. (2021) examined how audit fees affect AQ in China and found that audit fees and AQ are lower for firms audited by auditors in their early years of being signing auditors. In spite these mixed results, we write that:

H₁: Audit fees significantly influence AQ.

2.2 Auditor Independence and AQ

Chen et al. (2005) investigated auditor's independence and AQ in auditor-client negotiation over financial reporting issues using Taiwan data. They found a significant negative relation. Also, Suseno (2013) found that auditor's independence significantly influenced AQ. Rahmina and Agoes (2014) assessed auditor's independence and AQ and found a positive influence. Sarwoko and Agoes (2014) investigated the influence of auditor's independence on AQ of 50 public accounting firms which are registered in the Indonesian capital market. The results depicted that auditor's independence has significant influence on AQ. Tepalagul and Lin (2015) presented a comprehensive review of academic research pertaining to auditor independence and AQ during the period 1976-2013 in 9 leading journals related to auditing and concluded that there was mixed evidence.

Further, Octavia and Widodo (2015) assessed the effect of independence of auditors on AQ using 50 large public accounting firms in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Results of research conducted showed that auditor's independence has significant effect on AQ. Also, Saputra (2015) concluded that AQ is affected by the auditor's independence and that the more independent an auditor then increasing AQ. Aghaei (2016) examined the effect of auditor independence on AQ using 107 respondents and accepted it has impact. Tobi et al. (2016) examined auditor's independence and AQ and revealed a positive connection. Zahmatkesh and Rezazadeh (2017) investigated the effect of auditor independence AQ in Iran and found them to be significant. Furthermore, Iryani (2017) assessed the effect of auditors' independence on AQ in South Jakarta, Indonesia. Based on the findings, it was concluded that auditor's independence and AQ are positively significant. Zamzami et al. (2017) examined effects of auditor independence on AQ in Indonesia and observed that auditor's independence affect AQ.

Similarly, Amalia et al. (2019) examined the effect of auditor's independence on AQ of 45 Public Accountants in East Java, Indonesia. The result showed that the independence positively affected the AQ. Wahyuni et al. (2019) also found that auditor independence has a significant effect on AQ. Haeridistia and Fadjarenie (2019) explored the effect of auditor's independence on AQ in DKI Jakarta and showed that auditor's independence's affects AQ. Lamba et al. (2020) analyzed auditor independence and AQ in the Inspectorate of Regional Government, Papua Province, Indonesia. The results showed that auditor independence and AQ are positively significant.

Nwafor and Amahalu (2021) examined auditors' independence and AQ in Nigeria and showed a significant and positive relationship. Yixin (2021) assessed the effect of auditor's independence on AQ. The results indicated that independence has a significant effect on AQ. Hwang et al. (2022) investigated whether AQ is related to auditor independence in Korea. They found a significantly positive relationship. In spite of these mixed results, we write that: H₂: Auditor's independence significantly influence AQ. On the control variables, Sajadi et al. (2012) used 72 companies over 2010-2003 and confirmed that firm size has no significant effect on AQ. Also, Tobi et al. (2016) found (i) AQ and leverage and (ii) AQ and company

size both strongly, negatively and statistically significant. Ilechukwu (2017) also concluded that AQ is significant with client size and leverage. Pham et al. (2017) found that smaller audit firms provided better AQ. Sari et al. (2019) found accounting firm size did not affect AQ. Further, Yanti and Wijaya (2020) found firm size and AQ no effect.

3. Methods

The research design is correlational and the population is 16 publicly quoted industrial goods companies. 4 of the corporations are currently not trading because of reasons of below listing standards and missing regulatory filing. The sample consists of 12 companies actively engaged on the trading floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group. The model of the study is adapted from Yahaya and Awen (2021) with the control variables (leverage and firm size):

$$ADQT_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AF_{i,t} + \beta_2 AI_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 FSZ_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas ADQT is AQ measured by big4 auditors, "1" is assigned to companies using PWC, Deloitte, E&Y, KPMG and "0" if not (Abu et al., 2018; Abu et al., 2019ab; Abu et al., 2019b; Salawu et al., 2017a; Salawu et al., 2017b; Salawu et al., 2018).

AF is audit fees measured by log of total audit fee (Meidawati & Assidiqi, 2019; Sari et al., 2019; Behrend et al., 2020; Yanti & Wijaya, 2020; Cho et al., 2021; Chang et al., 2021).

AI is auditor's independence, measured by auditors' fee to revenue ratio (Haeridistia & Fadjarenie, 2019; Amalia et al., 2019; Wahyuni et al., 2019; Lamba et al., 2020; Nwafor & Amahalu, 2021; Yixin, 2021; Hwang et al., 2022).

LEV is leverage, measured by total debt to total assets (Gavana et al., 2017; Ilechukwu, 2017; Tobi et al., 2016; Yahaya & Andow; 2015; Yahaya & Lamido, 2022).

FSZ is firm size represented by log of assets (Agboola et al., 2020; Ilechukwu, 2017; Pahm et al., 2017; Sajadi et al., 2012; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021; Yanti & Wijaya, 2020; Yeosuf et al., 2017).

i = Corporation script ($i = 12$)

t = Year script ($t = 15$)

β_0 = Constant

β_{1-4} = Coefficients

ε = Error term

The dataset was obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the firms under consideration and analysed with the use of descriptive statistics, correlation, regression and its diagnostics which account for normality, homoscedasticity, multicollinearity of model residual, panel effects test and Hausman specification test. Note however, that these tests are conducted with 5% confidence interval. The next section deals with the results and discussion of the findings.

4. Results and Discussion

This is the results section of the article and Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics of the data that is used, which shows the observations, central mean, standard deviations, minimum and maximum means. The essence of the descriptive statistics is to enable the authors have a summary idea of the dataset they are dealing with.

Table 1: *Descriptive Statistics*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ADQT	180	.878	.328	0	1
AF	180	4.335	.448	2.68	5.8
AI	180	.579	.036	.434	.697
LEV	180	65.383	27.911	4.28	305.8
FS	180	7.482	.724	5.39	8.68

Source: Figures from STATA 14

From the results in Table 1, it is clear that the values of ADQT (AQ), which is the outcome variable are binary (between 0 and 1) and therefore, the appropriate regression model is either binary logic or Probit model. The table shows that the number of observations is 180 (12 firms over 15 years). Based on the figures in the table, AQ averages .878 with a standard deviation of .328, meaning the data is not volatile and the minimum and maximum means are 0 and 1, respectively. Similarly, audit fees (AF) averages 4.335 with a standard deviation of .448, meaning that the data is not risk-spread and the minimum and maximum means are 2.68 and 5.8. In the same view, audit independence (AI) averages .579 with a standard deviation of .036, suggesting that the data is not volatile and the minimum and maximum means are .434 and .697. On the control variables side, leverage (LEV) averages 65 percent with a standard deviation of 28 percent, meaning that the data is not volatile and the minimum and maximum means are 4 percent and 306 percent. These findings show that Nigeria industrial firms are highly geared. Firm size is in the region of 7.482 with a spread of .724, meaning that the data is not volatile and the minimum and maximum means are 5.39 and 8.68.

We also carry out correlation analysis which shows the bivariate relationship between two variables and the findings are presented in Table 2.

 Table 2: *Pairwise correlations*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) ADQT	1.000				
(2) AF	0.405*	1.000			
	(0.000)				
(3) AI	-0.080	0.262*	1.000		
	(0.284)	(0.000)			
(4) LEV	-0.365*	-0.253*	0.168*	1.000	
	(0.000)	(0.001)	(0.024)		
(5) FS	0.370*	0.842*	-0.187*	-0.316*	1.000
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.012)	(0.000)	

*** 1%, ** 5%, * 10%

Source: Figures from STATA 14

Several important findings could be deduced from Table 2; first it shows that AQ is positively and significantly correlated with audit fees (coeff = .405, sig-value = .000). These results are consistent with the works of Suseno (2013), Rahmina and Agoes (2014), Eshleman and Guo (2014), Idawati (2014), Hosseinniakani et al. (2014). Corbella et al. (2015), Saputra (2015), Jung et al. (2016), Salehi et al. (2017), Kuntari et al. (2017), Pham et al. (2017), Zamzami et al. (2018), Ibrahim and Ali (2018), Gunn et al. (2019), Hai et al. (2019), Wiguna et al. (2019), Gandia and Huguet (2020). Second, AQ is negatively and significantly correlated with leverage (coeff = -.365, sig-value = .000). These results are consistent with the works of Tobi et al. (2016) and Ilechukwu (2017). Third, AQ is positively and significantly correlated with firm size (coeff = .370, sig-value = .000). Findings are in agreement with the works of Sajadi et al. (2012), Ilechukwu (2017), Pham et al. (2017) and Yanti and Wijaya (2020). However, the statistical relationship between AQ and audit independence is non-significant. These findings are in agreement with the work of Tepalagul and Lin (2015).

We also embarked on regression analysis and the results are contained in Table 3. It should be noted, however, that these results are not for discussion. The purpose is to carry out regression diagnostics to enable the authors establish the final regression characteristics.

Table 3: OLS regression

ADQT	Coeff.	Std.Erro.	t-val.	p-val.	[95% Interval]	Sig
AF	.598	.143	4.18	.000	.316 .88	***
AI	-3.109	.994	-3.13	.002	-5.07 -1.148	***
LEV	-.003	.001	-3.58	.000	-.004 -.001	***
FS	-.207	.086	-2.40	.018	-.378 -.037	**
Constant	1.827	.628	2.91	.004	.587 3.067	***
R ²		0.278	Number of obs		180	
F-test		16.827	Prob > F		0.000	

*** 1%, ** 5%, * 10%

Source: Figures from STATA 14

The first regression diagnostic we conducted is check of normality of residual. The result shows that the residual is not normally distributed (p-value = .000). We are not surprised by this result, because with a response variable that is measured by binary, the data is not expected to be normally distributed. In view of this situation, we use three non-parametric

tests (Mann-Whitney Test, Kruskal-Wallis Test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test) for the final regression. We check for multicollinearity and the result shows that the mean VIF is 5.49 with audit fees having the highest VIF of 9.21. In view of these results, we lack the statistical evidence to support multicollinearity. Tables 4, 5, 6, and 7 show the findings of the final regression after taking into account these diagnostic results.

Table 4: *Non-parametric test results (Influence of AF on ADQT)*

Tests	Chi ²	P-value
Mann-Whitney	11.636	.000
Kruskal-Wallis	33.865	.0001
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	.6853	.000

Source: Figures from STATA 14

Table 4 shows that the p-value measuring the influence of audit fees on AQ is significant, therefore, hypothesis one is accepted. This finding is important because it shows that any increase in audit fees enhances AQ. This could be linked to the fact that the auditors would have been motivated. This result is consistent with the findings of Suseno (2013), Rahmina and Agoes (2014), Eshleman and Guo (2014), Idawati (2014), Hosseinniakani et al. (2014), Corbella et al. (2015), Saputra (2015), Jung et al. (2016), Salehi et al. (2017), Kuntari et al. (2017), Pham et al. (2017), Zamzami et al. (2018), Ibrahim and Ali (2018), Gunn et al. (2019), Hai et al. (2019), Wiguna et al. (2019), Gandia and Huguet (2020). However, this is not consistent with the findings of Hoitash et al. (2007), Choi et al. (2010), Yuniarti (2011), Asthana and Boone (2012), Krauß et al. (2015), Tepalagul and Lin (2015). Ilechukwu (2017), Meidawati and Assidiqi (2019), Sari et al. (2019), Wahyuni et al. (2019), Behrend et al. (2020), Yanti and Wijaya (2020), Cho et al. (2021), Chang et al. (2021). Table 5 presents the findings connecting audit independence with AQ.

Table 5: *Non-parametric test results (Influence of AI on ADQT)*

Tests	Chi ²	P-value
Mann-Whitney	6.314	.000
Kruskal-Wallis	3.777	.0052
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	.3613	.009

Source: Figures from STATA 14

Table 5 indicates that p-value of audit independence is significant. This finding implies that the more the external auditors are independent (without financial interest other the audit fees paid to them), the better the quality of the audit report. Therefore, hypothesis two is hereby accepted. This finding is consistent with the works of Chen et al. (2005), Suseno (2013), Rahmina and Agoes (2014), Sarwoko and Agoes (2014), Octavia and Widodo (2015), Saputra (2015), Tobi et al. (2016), Aghaei (2016), Iryani (2017), Zahmatkesh and Rezazadeh (2017), Zamzami et al. (2018), Haeridistia and Fadjarenie (2019), Amalia et al. (2019), Wahyuni et al. (2019), Lamba et al. (2020), Nwafor and Amahalu (2021), Yixin (2021), Hwang et al. (2022). However, it is inconsistent with the works of Tepalagul and Lin (2015). Table 6 shows the findings connecting one of the control variables, leverage with AQ.

Table 6: *Non-parametric test results (Influence of LEV on ADQT)*

Tests	Chi ²	P-value
Mann-Whitney	11.635	.000
Kruskal-Wallis	14.041	.0002
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	.4246	.001

Source: Figures from STATA 14

The finding in Table 6 is outside the a priori expectation of this research. It shows that highly leveraged firms have significant impact on AQ. This finding is consistent with the works of Tobi et al. (2016) and Ilechukwu (2017). This could be explained that highly geared firms would make sure that their audit reports are of high quality so that both existing and potential investors could invest in them.

Table 7: *Non-parametric test results (Influence of FSZ on ADQT)*

Tests	Chi ²	P-value
Mann-Whitney	11.635	.000
Kruskal-Wallis	24.057	.0001
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	.5345	.000

Source: Figures from STATA 14

Table 7 provides the evidence supporting the relationship between firm size and AQ. It shows that the nexus is significant as this finding is in line with the works of Sajadi et al. (2012), Ilechukwu (2017), Pham et al. (2017), and Yanti and Wijaya (2020).

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper examines the influences of audit fees and audit independence on AQ within the context of publicly quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings, we can draw several conclusions; first that audit fees are important determinant of AQ. Second, that audit independence is a determinant of AQ. Third, on control variables side, that both leverage and firm size are also determinants of AQ among Nigeria industrial goods firms. Based on these conclusions, we offer several recommendations; first, local audit firms should build capacity to be like one of the big4s. Second, the independence of the external auditors are sacrosanct and every effort must be invested in defending and protecting it. Finally, firms must maintain optimum capital structure and total assets so that they can benefit from both economies of scope and scale. The findings should be useful to the Nigerian regulators (the Nigerian Exchange Group, Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria, the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission). On the limitations side, like most empirical studies, this article is not protected from the choice of sector, model and analyses. It is noteworthy to state the obvious: the economy is weak, particularly, within the context of corporate governance.

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